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Research article

The time of acquisition of multispectral predictors matters: the role of seasonality in bird species distribution models

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Species distribution models (SDMs) analyse the relationships between species occurrences and environmental predictors. Their efficacy largely depends on the selection of ecologically relevant predictors, with remote sensing (RS) data being one of the most commonly used sources. The usability of multispectral predictors is influenced by temporal changes in vegetation and environmental conditions. However, the impact of seasonality is often overlooked, despite its potential to affect model accuracy. This study aims to assess the influence of seasonality in RS predictors on SDM performance for bird species. The study was conducted for an area of the Czech Republic, using presence–absence data from the Breeding Bird Survey (2018–2021) covering 147 survey squares and 104 bird species. We used Sentinel-2 satellite imagery to derive monthly and full-season composites of vegetation indices and reflectance bands from March to September (hereafter ‘periods’). Precipitation, terrain, and vegetation structure were also included. SDMs were constructed using Lasso-regularized logistic regression, and model performance was assessed through area under the ROC curve (AUC) and R^2 . Linear mixed-effects models were employed to evaluate model performance, temporal prediction stability, and predictor importance stability across all species. Our results show that model performance depends on the period from which the predictors were derived. This dependence varies significantly among species and is partially associated with habitat preferences and prevalence, with forest species exhibiting greater stability. Differences in model performance across periods aligned with shifts in predictor importance, causing different RS predictors to become significant with seasonal changes. In conclusion, seasonal changes in vegetation, as reflected in the temporal variability of RS predictors, significantly affect SDM performance and predictor selection. Although species’ ecological characteristics played a role, the effects remained species-dependent, making it difficult to develop universal recommendations. Nevertheless, accounting for seasonal variations in RS predictors can enhance model accuracy for many species.

Keywords: bird distribution, multispectral predictors, species distribution models, temporal variation

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Introduction

Species distribution models (SDMs), also known as environmental niche models (ENMs), are powerful tools used in ecology and conservation. They link species occurrence data with climatic and/or environmental information, enabling researchers to understand and predict species distributions across various landscapes and temporal scales (Ferrier et al. 2017). Consequently, SDMs are useful for a variety of applications, including conservation planning (Segal et al. 2021), managing invasive species (Bazzichetto et al. 2021), and assessing the effects of environmental change (Haesen et al. 2023). However, the accuracy and usability of these models heavily rely on the selection of ecologically relevant predictors (Williams et al. 2012, Fourcade et al. 2018, Davies et al. 2023).

In this context, remote sensing (RS) data have become increasingly important for identifying the key environmental variables that drive species distributions. By providing spatially explicit and regularly acquired data, RS helps capture a wide range of ecological factors that can enhance the predictive power of SDMs (Goetz et al. 2007, Zimmermann et al. 2007, Buermann et al. 2008, Saatchi et al. 2008, Cord and Rödder 2011, He et al. 2015, Tehrani et al. 2020, 2021, Chaparro et al. 2022). Environmental predictors derived from RS, such as climate, topography, or classified land cover maps, have been used in SDMs for a long time (Newton-Cross et al. 2007, Morán-Ordóñez et al. 2012, Rickbeil et al. 2014). More recently, it became possible to derive vegetation structure – an important indicator of habitat quality – from radar or LiDAR (Bergen et al. 2009, Moudrý et al. 2023a). At the same time, the use of continuous metrics such as normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and enhanced vegetation index (EVI), and/or raw spectral bands has become widespread. These indices and spectral variables serve as proxies for vegetation productivity and are often used to infer the spatial quantity and quality of certain resources, such as vegetation biomass or chlorophyll content (Pettorelli et al. 2011), thus improving model accuracy (Shirley et al. 2013, Arenas-Castro et al. 2022, Prajzlerová et al. 2024).

However, habitat characteristics such as land cover and vegetation productivity, which are key drivers of resource availability and species distribution at local scales (Pearson and Dawson 2003, Luoto et al. 2007), are not static over time. Multispectral satellite data, with the advantage of frequent and extensive data coverage, provide valuable insights into changes over time. They capture shifting patterns in land cover and vegetation, with reflectance values influenced by factors such as seasonal growth, plant stress, and weather conditions such as dry or wet periods. Additionally, phenology – the timing of biological events, e.g. flowering or leaf emergence – affects reflectance through parameters such as leaf maturation (Noda et al. 2021) and senescence (Moudrý et al. 2021). Together, these changing conditions allow the derivation of a wide range of multispectral predictors representing diverse environmental factors, which are relevant to the

species' presence or absence at different times. Despite the clear influence of temporal dynamics which is, for example, considered in disease distribution modelling (Liu et al. 2006, Franke and Menz 2007), SDM studies often focus heavily on spatial resolution while overlooking the temporal dimension of predictors (Chauvier et al. 2022, Moudrý et al. 2023b, Mazziotta et al. 2024). However, not accounting for temporal variation and failure to choose the most relevant times to capture the preferred habitat of the modelled species can potentially lead to a significant decrease in SDMs' accuracies, particularly when using unclassified multispectral data as the source of predictors.

There are several commonly used approaches for selecting the time periods from which RS data should be used in SDMs: 1) selecting predictor values from the closest available date to species sampling or from a composite of images within the sampling period to ensure alignment between environmental conditions and species occurrence (Pickens and King 2014, Bonthoux et al. 2018, Araújo et al. 2019, Wellmann et al. 2020), though this can be impractical for large-scale studies due to cloud cover and data availability limitations (Regos et al. 2020, Arenas-Castro et al. 2022); 2) using long-term averages, such as seasonal, annual, or multi-year RS composites (He et al. 2015, Fick and Hijmans 2017), which offer stable representations of habitat conditions but may overlook short-term variability; 3) focusing on extreme environmental events, such as floods, droughts, or heatwaves, which can significantly shape habitat availability and, in some cases, better explain species distributions than average conditions (Zimmermann et al. 2009, Bateman et al. 2012, Briscoe et al. 2016, Feldmeier et al. 2018); in RS, this approach involves extracting the minimum or maximum values from all available images over a given time period; and (4) incorporating variability measures, such as SD or the coefficient of variation over time, to account for seasonal fluctuations in habitat conditions, capturing temporal dynamics that may be missed if using static averages (Arenas-Castro et al. 2022, Rousseau and Betts 2022).

Rather than relying on approaches such as using seasonal characteristics or matching predictor values to the species sampling date, we suggest that the time most relevant for selecting RS predictors is the time when the key environmental features are most distinguishable. This timing may not necessarily align with the species observation date and may vary across different habitats. Few studies have examined the influence of temporality in predictors on SDM performance (Feldmeier et al. 2018, Fernandez et al. 2018, Andrew and Fox 2020). Moreover, these studies often overlook the role of habitat preferences, which can influence model performance and its variation across different periods. As the distribution of functional groups of birds is shaped by different aspects of the environment (Morelli et al. 2024), habitat structure, food availability, and climatic conditions affect species differently based on their ecological traits and behaviors. Previous research has shown that model performance varies by species' habitat preferences (Hallman and Robinson 2020, Morelli et al. 2024), and we assume that certain habitats may

be impacted by phenological stages to a greater or smaller degree, as captured in RS imagery.

Our study aimed to assess how seasonality in RS predictors affects the performance of SDMs for various bird species in the Czech Republic, a central European country characterized by a mosaic of diverse farmlands, forests, wetlands, and urban habitats, and whose spectral reflectance varies strongly over the four seasons. We propose that (as different habitats are distinguishable at different times), the performance of bird SDMs depends both on the timing of imagery acquisition and on species-specific habitat preferences. Additionally, we hypothesized that altitude affects the model performance as the time of phenological shifts and vegetation greening depends on elevation. Consequently, we expect species with broader altitudinal ranges to be more challenging to model accurately, because of the variability in how RS predictors appear at different altitudes.

Material and methods

Study area

The study area is situated in the Czech Republic, located in central Europe. The geography includes a variety of hills, plateaus, and lowlands, with mountain ranges marking the boundaries. Elevations range from 115 to 1603 m a.s.l. The landscape is characterized by temperate forests, agricultural

lands, inland waterways, and urban zones. The climate in this region is temperate, with a distinct four-season cycle.

Species data

Species data were derived from the Breeding Bird Survey Czechia (organized by the Czech Society for Ornithology), launched in 2018, which is based on the principles of citizen science, involving a voluntary collaboration of skilled ornithologists in field data collection. We used data from the breeding season (counts are conducted twice annually: 12 April–10 May and 15 May–10 June).

Site selection follows a stratified random approach, where the availability of observers is a stratum, established by the Breeding Bird Survey in the UK (Newson et al. 2005), and more recently applied in Hungary (Szép et al. 2012). Volunteers choose general areas where they wish to count, and a computer randomly selects one of the squares (approximately 2.8×3 km within a 10 km radius of the chosen center). The observer establishes two line transects, each exactly 1 km long, that are as straight as possible. The lines must be at least 500 m apart, and they should be more than 250 m from the edge of the square to avoid double-counting the same bird. This method ensures the representativeness of the obtained data, providing a reliable depiction of bird populations across the Czech Republic (Reif et al. 2022).

We used breeding data collected from 2018 to 2021, which provided information for 147 squares (Fig. 1) and a dataset

Figure 1. The Czech Republic, covered by the squares (approx. 8 km^2 each) where sampling was conducted. The displayed land cover is based on data from the Corine database.

containing presences and derived absences for 166 species. We selected species with more than 10 and fewer than 137 presences to ensure sufficient data for reliable model training, while avoiding highly prevalent species that might bias the analysis, resulting in a final total of 104 species.

For the classification of species according to their preferred habitat, we used AVONET: morphological, ecological, and geographical data for all birds (Tobias et al. 2022). We distinguished six habitat types, forest, woodland, shrubland, wetland, human-modified, and grassland. Each species is associated with only one habitat type. We also classified species based on the mean elevation and elevation range at which they occur in the Czech Republic. This information was derived from species occurrences in the Czech Species Occurrence Database.

Remote sensing data

We used Sentinel-2 satellite imagery from the Copernicus Earth Engine Catalog (COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED) with a spatial resolution of 30 m. The images were processed with a cloud-masking function, using the 'QA60' band to eliminate pixels affected by clouds, ensuring high-quality data for further analysis.

We used individual bands and vegetation indices in our analysis, as they have been shown to be significant predictors of species distribution (Shirley et al. 2013, Arenas-Castro et al. 2022). Because individual bands and vegetation indices are strongly intercorrelated and the correlation coefficients can vary throughout the vegetation season, we aimed to select predictors that are ecologically relevant while minimizing correlation across the entire vegetation season. This resulted in selecting green band, along with two indices: the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and the modified normalized difference water index (MNDWI).

Our analysis focused on imagery from 2018 to 2021, consistent with our species data collection period. First, we generated composites for each month of the vegetation season, spanning March to September. Second, we calculated

maximum and minimum reflectance and vegetation indices values across the whole season to capture extreme values (hereafter *season_max* and *season_min*). Third, we calculated median values and SDs for the whole March-to-September period (hereafter *season_med* and *season_het*). From individual bands and vegetation indices in each period, we calculated the median and SD for each square, the former representing landscape composition and the latter quantifying habitat heterogeneity (Table 1).

Other predictors

To capture all potential predictors influencing species distribution, we included precipitation, terrain, and vegetation structure (Table 1; temperature correlated with the terrain and, therefore, was excluded from the final models). The precipitation values were derived from measurements provided by the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute, using daily rasters at a 1 km resolution to calculate the mean precipitation for each period. The terrain was expressed as the difference between the highest and lowest points in a square (Moudrý and Šimová 2013). For vegetation structure, we used the SD of vegetation height data from the GEDI L3 Gridded Land Surface Metrics, ver. 2 dataset (Dubayah 2021), obtained from the ORNL DAAC.

Groups of predictors

From all derived predictors, we created 13 predictor groups (for each species, we then developed 13 models, each using one of these predictor groups as input). First, we defined period-specific predictor groups, which included the green band, MNDWI, NDVI, and precipitation – calculated separately for each period – along with temporally constant predictors: terrain and vegetation. Hereafter, we refer to these groups (periods) and the models based on them as March, April, May, June, July, August, September, *season_max*, *season_min*, *season_med*, and *season_het*. Additionally, to assess whether the model performance improves by combining predictors across multiple periods, we developed two

Table 1. Description of predictors used in SDMs. Predictors with two calculation methods per square (median/SD) resulted in two different predictors per period.

Predictor	Calculation frequency	Calculation method per square	Description
Green	Separately for each period	Median/SD	Green band; sensitive to the chlorophyll content in plants, making it effective in detecting healthy vegetation and distinguishing between different types of vegetation cover
MNDWI	Separately for each period	Median/SD	Modified normalized difference water index (green – short wave infrared) / (green + short wave infrared); designed to enhance open water features, also helps in distinguishing built-up area features from open water, which may be problematic with other indices
NDVI	Separately for each period	Median/SD	Normalized difference vegetation index (near infrared – red) / (near infrared + red); useful for assessing vegetation cover and greenness, which directly relates to habitat quality
Precipitation	Separately for each period	Median	Precipitation directly influences habitat characteristics and resource availability
Terrain	Constant across all periods	Max and min altitude difference	Difference between the lowest and highest elevations inside the square; shapes microclimates, vegetation, or resource availability
Vegetation	Constant across all periods	Median	Vegetation structure directly influences habitat suitability for birds by providing nesting sites, foraging opportunities and shelter

other models: one using principal component analysis (PCA), which combines predictors into principal components (used components accounted for 85% of predictor variability), and another one using the variance inflation factor (VIF)-based stepwise selection (threshold = 2; package 'usdm' for R (www.r-project.org), [Naimi et al. 2017](#)). For both techniques, we set them to select a number of predictors comparable to the period-specific models to ensure result comparability. Hereafter, we refer to these models as PCA and VIF.

Species distribution models

We applied the Lasso regularization technique (package 'glmnet' for R, [Friedman et al. 2010](#), [Tay et al. 2023](#)) to logistic regression models with a logit link function to develop species distribution models (SDMs). This method combines feature selection with regularization, reducing overfitting by driving less important coefficients to zero, resulting in simpler, more interpretable models ([Reineking and Schröder 2006](#)). All predictors were scaled to ensure consistent analysis.

For each species, we fitted 13 models, each corresponding to a different predictor group, resulting in 1352 models. Next, we applied a cross-validated Lasso regularization procedure, adjusting the regularization parameter (lambda) to optimize model performance using the area under the curve (AUC) as the evaluation metric. We used AUC as the primary metric of model performance; for completeness, we also calculated the McFadden Pseudo-R² for each model. To evaluate the sensitivity of model performance to a specific period, we calculated the Δ AUC, which represents the difference between the AUC for a given period and the highest AUC observed for the species, and the AUC range (i.e. the difference in AUC between the best- and the worst-performing model) for each species.

Post hoc modelling of SDM performance

To further understand what could cause the observed differences in model performances, we fitted several models. First, we investigated the possible differences in model performance between periods and habitat types by fitting a linear mixed model (package 'lme4' for R, [Bates et al. 2015](#)) with AUC as a response variable using habitat type and period as categorical fixed effects and species as a random intercept term. Because including a habitat–period interaction only led to a 1.5% increase in explained variability (Nakagawa's marginal R²; [Nakagawa et al. 2017](#)) while increasing the AIC value by 430 points, this interaction was removed from further modelling. To determine which categories of habitat/period differed significantly in their SDM performance, we then performed multiple comparisons using Tukey contrasts based on the Kenward–Roger covariance matrix and degrees of freedom adjustment (package 'emmeans' for R; [Lenth 2025](#)). Additionally, we explored potential causes for the observed differences in model performance between species. Second, to understand what influences the model sensitivity to period, we fitted a linear model with the species-level AUC range as the response and species prevalence, habitat type, elevation range, and mean elevation (across the given species

observations) as predictors. To allow for non-linear relationships, we added quadratic terms to all continuous predictors in all models. If a quadratic term of a given predictor was insignificant, we kept only its linear term in the model.

Predictor importance

The relative importance of individual predictors in SDMs was determined for all models except PCA and VIF, as these models used a different set of predictors. To assess predictor importance, we employed a permutation-based approach as described by [Thuiller et al. \(2009\)](#). The values of each predictor were randomly shuffled and, for each model, the correlation (Pearson correlation coefficient, r) between the predictions from the model based on the original data and the one based on the shuffled data was computed. These steps (shuffling and correlation) were performed 100 times and an average correlation coefficient (\bar{r}) was computed. High average correlation meant that the predictions were unaffected by shuffling the predictor, inducing its low importance. Therefore, the predictor importance (PI) was defined as $1 - \bar{r}$. This approach provides insights into the relative influence of each predictor on model performance while controlling for the effects of other predictors.

To assess how the importance of individual predictors varies across periods, we characterized each model by a vector of importances corresponding to all predictors (always keeping the same order of predictors). Subsequently, we calculated the mean pair-wise Euclidean distance between these vectors for each species, acquiring a new quantity named 'predictor importance variability' (PIV) quantifying how much the predictor importances differ across the models for different periods. Finally, we tried to explain the variation in PIV by regressing it against the best-achieved AUC, AUC range, prevalence, mean elevation at which the species occurs, elevation range, and habitat type.

Results

Models performance

The mean AUC (\pm SD) for all 1352 models was 0.775 (\pm 0.085). Of these, 814 models achieved an AUC greater than 0.7, and 98 out of 104 species had at least one model with an AUC greater than 0.7. The mean McFadden's pseudo-R² (\pm SD) for all models was 0.196 (\pm 0.117). Both performance metrics (AUC and McFadden's pseudo-R²) were highly correlated (0.898 Pearson correlation), which further justified our use of only one of them (AUC) in the rest of the results.

The linear mixed-effects model showed that AUC varied significantly with both period and habitat type ([Fig. 2](#)). Of the total 12.3% variability in AUC explained by the fixed effects (marginal Nakagawa's R²), habitat type accounted for 10.7%, leaving only 1.6% to the effect of period. To be more specific, pairwise comparisons revealed that wetland species models yielded significantly higher AUC values than forest and woodland species models. Regarding period-based differences, significant inter-period variations in AUC were

Figure 2. Boxplots illustrating the distribution of Δ AUC values for different models across various habitat types. The x-axis represents different periods, while the y-axis shows Δ AUC, representing the difference between the AUC for a given period and the best-performing period for each species. Individual data points are plotted over the boxplots.

observed. Overall, the VIF and PCA predictors outperformed other groups of predictors in four comparisons. Among period-specific models, June and September were the best-performing, achieving higher AUC values than other models in three comparisons. The min_values were the worst predictors, showing the lowest performance in 10 comparisons. Additionally, season_het and season_max performed worse than other predictor groups in five and three comparisons, respectively. More details on the pairwise comparisons can be found in the Supporting information.

Effects of the period

The largest AUC range for a given species was found in models for the tufted duck *Aythya fuligula*, with a range of 0.265 (AUC 0.713–0.977). In contrast, the smallest AUC range was seen in the Eurasian wren *Troglodytes troglodytes*, with a range of 0.032 (AUC 0.875–0.907). The observed variability in model performance across periods can be attributed to species prevalence and habitat type, explaining 26% of this variability (Fig. 3). We found that forest habitats exhibit

significantly greater consistency in modelling, suggesting they are less susceptible to temporal variability. However, vegetation structure (a non-seasonal GEDI predictor) emerged as the most important predictor. In contrast, species associated with human-modified and woodland habitats showed lower stability in predictions across periods (Fig. 3).

Predictor importance

Predictor importance was evaluated only for the period-specific models, as the VIF and PCA models relied on different sets of predictors, making direct comparisons not feasible. Furthermore, only predictors from models with an AUC > 0.7 were included, as this threshold indicates fair predictive performance (Araújo et al. 2005), and we considered it meaningful to include predictors only from models that provide explanatory value. The predictor importance in successful models varied considerably with habitat type and period (Fig. 4). For forest species, vegetation structure was consistently the most important predictor, though its importance decreased slightly later in the

Figure 3. The dependence of the AUC range for each species on habitat type (left) and species prevalence (right) from a linear model containing habitat type, species prevalence, and elevation at which the species occur and elevation range as predictors. The whiskers (for habitat categories) and shaded areas (for continuous prevalence values) correspond to the 95% confidence intervals. The predictions for given variables are made while keeping all other variables at their average observed value (continuous predictors) or at their reference level (forest for habitat type factor), respectively.

season (July–September), when $NDVI_{MEDIAN}$ gained a bit higher relevance. Grassland species were best predicted by vegetation structure and median green band ($green_{MEDIAN}$), with minor contributions of terrain, $MNDWI_{MEDIAN}$ and $NDVI_{MEDIAN}$. In human-modified habitats, the most important predictors shifted over time: in March, precipitation, $green_{MEDIAN}$, and terrain were the key predictors. From April to June, however, $NDVI_{SD}$ and $NDVI_{MEDIAN}$ became more important. In later months (June–September), and for the season_med model, $green_{MEDIAN}$ was the most important parameter. For shrubland species, terrain and $green_{MEDIAN}$ alternated in importance, with terrain playing a greater role earlier in the season and for season_min and season_max models, while $green_{MEDIAN}$ was more important later in the season. Wetland species primarily relied on terrain and $MNDWI_{SD}$, with precipitation and $green_{MEDIAN}$ being significant at the start of the season, and $NDVI_{SD}$ becoming important for the season_max model. Woodland species showed more balanced predictor importance, with no single predictor dominating across periods. $Green_{SD}$ and precipitation were generally the least important predictors across all habitat types.

The predictor importance variability (PIV) for a given species differed significantly between habitat types (Fig. 5 left), with wetland species exhibiting the most stable predictor selection, while woodland species showed the greatest variability. PIV was also significantly decreasing with elevation in the higher altitudes (above 450 m a.s.l.; Fig. 5 right). Both prevalence and elevation range were found to be insignificant. All these predictors together explained approximately 23% of the PIV.

We did not find any association between the best achieved AUC and the AUC range (Fig. 6 left). However, we found a significant moderately strong positive correlation ($r=0.63$) between the AUC range and PIV, and a weak significant

negative correlation ($r=-0.34$) between PIV and the best achieved AUC (Fig. 6).

Discussion

In our study, we modelled the species distribution of 104 Czech bird species and successfully developed at least one well-performing model for most of them. However, model performance varied across species. Previously, it has been shown that SDMs of habitat specialists and species with more defined habitat requirements tend to perform better than those of habitat generalists, which typically show lower model accuracy (McPherson and Jetz 2007, Hallman and Robinson 2020, Morelli et al. 2024). This aligns with our results which, similar to McPherson and Jetz (2007), found that the highest accuracy was detected for wetland species, which have more specific environmental requirements. We initially hypothesized that model performance would be influenced by each species' altitudinal range, with phenology as a key driver of differences in predictors. Phenology is significantly affected by altitude; higher elevations typically experience cooler temperatures and a delayed onset of seasonal events such as flowering and leafing. Therefore, we expected that species with broader altitudinal ranges would be more challenging to model due to the differing multispectral images of the same habitats at various elevations. However, our results did not support this assumption.

Our study focused on the temporal resolution of predictors and we have shown that, for a substantial proportion of modelled bird species, temporal resolution of predictors matters. The finding that temporally specific predictions can lead to different results aligns with other studies (Feldmeier et al. 2018, Fernandez et al. 2018, Andrew and Fox 2020). However, unlike most studies focusing on climatic data and

Figure 4. Boxplots showing the distribution of predictor importances in models fitted on predictors from different periods, and for species from different habitat types. Only models with AUC greater than 0.7 were used.

Figure 5. Predictions of the linear model of the predictor importance variability (PIV) on habitat type and the mean elevation at which the species occur. The model also included insignificant effects of elevation range at which the species occur and of species prevalence. The shaded areas and whiskers correspond to the pointwise 95% confidence intervals. The predictions for a given predictor are made while keeping all other predictors at their average observed value (continuous predictors) or at their reference level (forest for habitat type factor), respectively.

extreme events (Briscoe et al. 2016, Feldmeier et al. 2018), our research evaluated optical RS predictors from several periods, commonly used in SDMs. Araújo et al. (2019), in their ‘golden standards for SDM’, state that predictor variables should capture the conditions on which the response variable actually depends at relevant temporal resolutions. However, applying this standard is not always straightforward, particularly for birds. Unlike many organisms, birds are highly mobile (Fuller 2012), suitable habitats for foraging and nesting can vary, and the temporal resolution of RS imagery capturing these aspects may differ. Even the same habitats undergo significant spectral changes throughout the

year, making it important to capture biotopes at their ‘spectral optimum’, when they are most distinguishable from non-preferred biotopes for effective modelling with multispectral data. Our results support this assumption, showing significant differences in model performance and predictor selection across various time periods, underscoring the complexity of applying this principle to bird species.

In exploring how temporal predictor selection influences model performance, we found notable differences between the approaches. Our pairwise comparison revealed that using extremes across periods was the least effective option, and variation over time also showed limited performance. Long-term

Figure 6. Pairwise correlations between the model performance (best achieved AUC for a given species), performance sensitivity to period (AUC range), and predictor importance variability (PIV).

averages performed moderately well but often underperformed compared to other periods. Matching the sampling date corresponds to the April–June periods when species data were collected. June performed best among period-based predictors, as did September (even though it was not part of the sampling period). This suggests that strong performance based on June data is due to spectral characteristics allowing differentiation among the preferred habitats in that month, rather than direct sampling alignment. Combining predictors from all periods using PCA and VIF models yielded the best results in pairwise comparisons. However, this approach was not universally optimal, as many species were still better modelled using individual periods, highlighting the species-specific nature of temporal resolution effects.

Further investigating the drivers of these temporal variations, we observed an effect of habitat type and species prevalence. Forest species exhibited significantly greater stability compared to other habitat types. However, this stability is primarily driven by the vegetation structure, which dominates these models, since this predictor is constant across all periods and not time-sensitive. Despite this stability, model accuracy for these species was the lowest, suggesting that the periodic RS predictors underperformed in this case and vegetation structure was more important for these species. This is in line with previous studies that have also shown vegetation structure to be a good predictor for modelling distribution of multiple bird species (Goetz et al. 2007, Burns et al. 2020). Our results also suggest that predictions for species with intermediate prevalence are more stable across different temporal resolutions of predictors. However, this may be a statistical artifact (Santika 2011); furthermore, the overall variability explained by our model was only 26%, indicating that the instability between predictions remains strongly species-dependent.

We have also demonstrated that species with a larger AUC range tend to exhibit greater variability in predictor selection (Fig. 6). Different RS predictors may become significant in different periods due to changes in vegetation phenology and other habitat features over the year. The stability in predictor selection, similar to other model characteristics, is also habitat- and elevation-dependent. Wetland species exhibited significantly greater stability in predictor selection. This is primarily because their distributions were modelled by two dominant predictors – terrain heterogeneity and the MNDWI. MNDWI effectively distinguishes water surfaces, while terrain heterogeneity, in the context of the Czech Republic, can serve as an indicator of water presence (Gábor et al. 2022). Water surfaces are predominantly located in lowland areas, which are characterized by low terrain heterogeneity, further reinforcing the stability of these predictors for wetland species. In contrast, woodland species showed the least stability in predictor selection. We hypothesize that these species are associated with less continuous tree cover compared to forest species, making vegetation structure a less reliable predictor in this case. At the same time, phenological changes have a strong effect on predictor selection in models for woodland species throughout the season. However, it needs to be

pointed out that the overall predictor importance variability (PIV) for all species included in our evaluation explained by our model was only 21%. This indicates that even though the association between the habitat and PIV is statistically significant, species-specific factors still play an important role.

Beside this, we have also showed that the green band can serve as a good predictor for modelling bird species distribution – for many species, it has been one of the most influential predictors in our models. On the other hand, the traditionally used predictor NDVI was, surprisingly, not among the most important predictors in our study. This aligns with findings by McFarland et al. (2012) who noted a variability in the usefulness of NDVI in predicting distribution of avian communities. However, the specific performance of individual optical bands in predicting bird distribution is often not explicitly detailed in studies. Instead, studies typically only integrate optical RS data with other types of data (such as microwave, LiDAR, or climatic data) to enhance model accuracy without partitioning their specific contribution to the models (Buermann et al. 2008, Singh et al. 2017).

In conclusion, our study demonstrates that the time of acquisition of predictors, capturing seasonal changes in vegetation characteristics, significantly affects SDMs. While the stability of model performance across different periods is to some extent influenced by habitat and other ecological characteristics, the impact of the period remains highly species-dependent, making universal recommendations difficult. Models combining predictors from all periods performed generally slightly better than period-based predictor groups, making this option preferable. However, when feasible, testing multiple periods remains the best approach to capturing the varying ecological conditions affecting species distribution.

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Author contributions

Dominika Prajzlerová: Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review and editing (lead). **Vojtěch Barták:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Software (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Petr Balej:** Data curation (equal); Software (equal);

Writing – original draft (equal). **Vítězslav Moudrý**: Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Petra Šimová**: Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (lead); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal).

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Data are available from the Figshare Digital Repository: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28816217> (Prajzlerová et al. 2025).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

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